

ABOUT FAMILY VALUES IN KARAKALPAK FAMILIES

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Abstract. The article deals with questions about family values in traditional families of the Karakalpak. The author also emphasizes the role of national customs and traditions in the upbringing of modern youth and preparing them for family life.

Keywords: family values, customs, traditions, the formation of spirituality and patriotism, worldview.

I. INTRODUCTION

Huge changes in the life of society, the technical capabilities of television, radio, media press are increasing every day. At the same time, the issues of studying customs and traditions in the process of modernizing society, their importance in the life of society are also increasing, but as globalization processes deepen, the formation of spirituality and worldview of the individual decreases. Of course, in order for customs and traditions to fulfill their purpose, they must be directly recognized by people and become an integral part of everyday life. For this reason, every society is interested in the fact that the traditions are well absorbed by the people.

Traditions and customs have a special historical significance, they arise under the influence of the material and social conditions of life, are consolidated over time and transmitted from generation to generation. To do this, they must become a value in human life. After all, customs, traditions and rituals enrich a person's life when they become a value for a person. Therefore, any society, any social system needs them,

with their help it is possible to expand relations between people, to create certain rules and criteria of morality.

Family, neighbors, mahalla aksakals and elders play an important role in shaping people's respect for traditions, rituals and customs. Modern socio-economic processes taking place in our republic have influenced the spirituality of the people, caused changes in many traditions and customs, are reflected in the formation of new traditions and rituals, because the family in which a child grows up becomes a model of his future family.

II. MAIN PART

The word family is known to everyone from a very early age. This is the most valuable thing in life. Family and family values in all countries of the world have always been at the heart of any society. [2, P.18] Therefore, this research work is relevant. It must be emphasized here that a special interest in family life has emerged in recent years in connection with the crisis state of the modern family, this is especially noticeable in the West. [5, P.20]

The family has long been considered the most important thing in a person's life. The family is also the most important agent of the child's socialization. Gradually, spiritual values fade into the background, including family values. Parents in the modern rhythm of life have almost no time to talk with their children. So it turns out that the child finds himself in a situation of dissonance regarding family values.

Based on the study of scientific sources, the family is one of the greatest values created by mankind in the entire history of its existence. No nation, no culture is complete without a family. [7, P.34] There is indeed a social need for the family, because if it were to disappear, the very existence of mankind would be in jeopardy. The family lays the foundation for the ideological, aesthetic, moral, philosophical experience of the child, his ideas about good and evil, the foundations of the mental, moral and physical appearance of the future citizen of modern society. [2, P.13] Throughout its history, mankind has not created - and probably never will create - the

best institution of education. Special studies by psychologists and educators have convincingly proved that not a single educational institution can give children what a normal family atmosphere gives, a child's communication with his father and mother. We must constantly remember that we are raising not only a child, but a citizen and a person. [6, P.99]

What does value mean? This is the importance, significance, benefit, usefulness of something. Family values are customs and traditions that are passed down from generation to generation. These are the feelings that make a family strong. This is everything that people experience together inside the house - joy and sorrow, well-being or problems and difficulties.

Love, trust and mutual assistance still lie at the heart of the values of the modern unit of society. However, times are changing, each era brings with it something new, progressive. Our society has become freer and more open. These factors influence the formation of the worldview of our citizens. [3, P.15] In order for parents to be able to pass on their experience of cultivating family values to their child, and for the child to begin to bring this experience into society, it is important to understand all the psychological problems associated with family values.

Love: this is the main family value. It manifests itself in tenderness towards loved ones, the desire to take care of them, protect them, and be constantly there.

Trust: It is important to learn to trust each other and teach your children to do so.

Kindness: this is the desire to help the weak, the defenseless, to support him, the need to be useful. Such relationships make the family more harmonious.

Fidelity: another guarantee of the strength of love bonds. Willingness to be with a loved one both in grief and in joy, in spite of any temptations.

Mutual understanding: it is important to understand each other perfectly, to respect the interests and aspirations of your soulmate and children.

Respect: it is expressed in respect for the individuality of each family member, the inadmissibility of "breaking" one spouse to the interests and needs of the other,

non-interference in the affairs of the young by the parents.

Everything good and bad is laid down for a person from childhood. He learns from examples, adopts experience, a model of behavior and attitudes towards others. One of the most accessible ways to do this naturally and naturally is through tradition. In each family, they can be completely different, but they solve one important task - to unite and strengthen. It is important that every member of the family knows that he is loved, appreciated, needed. Even being a close-knit family, each member of the family should be allocated space and given freedom for activities.

Flexibility in solving family problems is the path to happiness and a sense of comfort. Each family has its own order, daily routine, structure, rules. But too many rules and order can lead to a deterioration in relationships and the appearance of resentment. Honesty forms a deep bond between family members. Encourage honesty by practicing understanding, respecting whatever actions your loved ones do.

You need to learn to forgive the people who offended you. Everyone makes mistakes. Life is too short to waste it on resentment. Family values form in a small person an understanding of the role of the family, its significance and uniqueness. It is in the environment of loved ones that children learn to correctly express their feelings, kindness and generosity, respect and responsibility for their actions, love, trust and honesty.

The main task of modern society is the preservation of family values. Simple rules and moral principles, formed within the home, are then transferred to society. Generic values form a person's culture, make society more humane. The change and development of society, new views also form a new understanding of family values.

Of course, such concepts as trust, love, mutual assistance, respect and kindness remain fundamental for a person of the 21st century. But, sadly, they are under pressure from a variety of factors that are caused by the problems of society.

In the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the main criteria that form family and life values are the history of the clan, national customs, traditions, and spiritual heritage.

They find their expression in all spheres of life, not only of the family, but of our entire society.

Today, in the age of robotization and the development of high technologies, the personal qualities of a person are of particular relevance - the manifestation of love and respect for ancestors, the Motherland, loved ones, responsiveness, empathy, emotional intelligence, etc. Trends towards automation of routine processes in production cycles lead to an increase in the value of the creative component of the personality, including that arising from the originality of the culture in which it was brought up. High competition in the service sector also requires today's youth, seeking to integrate into the world community, the so-called "soft skills" that allow them to communicate effectively and create new values. In this regard, it is important to consider folk art, cultural traditions from the point of view of the encyclopedic set of rules, moral national and universal principles, norms that have shown successful experience in educating generations. [4, P.237-240]

Of course, the transmission of moral and aesthetic norms is fruitful only if it is consistent with the fundamental requirements of both society as a whole and the needs of the younger generation. For example, for modern Karakalpakstan youth, the needs for self-affirmation, the development of creative skills, and communication are relevant, therefore, family education should take into account such needs that can replenish knowledge and experience, develop new, high needs and ideals. Such an effective tool for the development and realization of the needs of a young person is the organic relationship between the moral and aesthetic aspects of national culture. This is probably why the dissatisfaction of these needs leads a person to degradation, spiritual passivity, emotional callousness.

Abu Rayhan Beruni believed that the lack of proper emotional education in the development of a young person nullifies any efforts of parents in transferring knowledge and experience. [8, P.32-33] The spiritual wealth of the Karakalpak people, their customs and traditions play a key role in the education of patriotism, love for the

Motherland, and social responsibility. It is thanks to these values that love for the native land, its historical and artistic heritage arises. In Karakalpak families, oral art plays a special role, which is rightfully considered the historical memory of the people, passed down from generation to generation and reflected in epics, legends, songs, epics. For example, such legends as "Alpamys", "Forty Girls", where love for the Motherland, family values, love for the place where he was born, national values that will be unforgettable in the future, were sung to the highest level. Especially reasonable relations between wife and husband, their courage, their deep love for each other, their place and role in society and in family life, their advice and wise words spoken to young people are an example of family education. [1, P.7-8]

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Therefore, it is necessary to revive national values in a natural way, through the awareness of national identity. Cultural traditions, the spiritual heritage of the people for many millennia were considered the primary source of spiritual growth. And today they are the most important factor in educating the younger generation in the spirit of devotion to their country and the ideals of humanism.

The family is one of the most multifaceted phenomena of social life, accompanying mankind from ancient times to the present day. In the modern world, the attitude towards the family as the main social institution has changed. This is due to the loss of the leading positions of the large patriarchal family, the increase in the independence of the younger generation. Indeed, the modern family cannot be the only source of information for the younger generation. Developing information technologies make it possible to use the widest databases and conduct comparative analysis. Nevertheless, the family still remains the most important source for the formation of ideas about the ethno-cultural and moral traditions of society. The child is given such family value concepts as "parental home" and his "future family".

In family relationships, mutual respect and trust should be valued, love and care for each other, the opportunity to realize oneself outside the family, family unity and

solidarity, communication, the opportunity to receive support in difficult times, friendly relations between children and parents. The past generation was brought up in the strictness of family traditions, passed down from mouth to mouth, and strictly observed by the descendants of the families. Since in the modern world there is absolutely no time left for a parent to educate family values, therefore they should be taught in educational institutions.

IV. CONCLUSION

Thus, the destruction of the institution of the family and family relations leads to the loss of moral well-being by society. The family is the cradle of the human personality, the school of virtue and the best human feelings. All-round harmonious development of the child is unthinkable without family education. The relevance of this issue allows us to conclude that the traditions of family education in the modern world are of high importance. Customs and traditions are two adjacent channels through which older generations pass on to the young the experience of their social behavior, their moral and political convictions and feelings, methods and techniques of social activity. At the same time, we must not forget that each generation has its own unique and unique history, cherishes its values and relies on them. We, as their bearers, may not notice these values, but they determine our behavior and lifestyle. Even if family values are not fully understood by young people as a social institution, the family is still a value for them.

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